

NOTES

Synthesis of Some Sulphanilamido-Benzo-thiazolyl Thiazole Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents

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It is observed from the survey of literature that the sulphanilamides possess biological activity¹⁻⁶. In view of this activity associated with thiazole and sulphanilamide moieties in Organic compounds, it was considered of interest to prepare 2-substituted thiazoles, having 2'-aminobenzothiazole and 4'-phenylsulphanilamides residue at 4-position.

p-Acetamido-*w*-chloroacetophenone reacted smoothly with substituted aryl thioamides in ethyl alcohol to give 2-substituted-4-(4'-acetamidophenyl)-thiazoles. These 4'-acetamidophenyl compounds were hydrolysed by 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, to their 4'-amino compounds (I) which were condensed with *p*-substituted benzenesulphonyl chlorides in presence of dry pyridine to give the corresponding sulphonamido/sulphanilamido compounds(II) in good yield. The 4'-aminophenyl compounds (I) were converted to 1-[4(4'-phenyl)thiazolyl]-thioureas by Vijaykumaran⁷ method and cyclised by sulphuryl chloride⁸ using chlorobenzene as solvent to 4-[6'(2'-amino)-benzothiazolyl]-thiazoles(III) which are condensed with *p*-substituted benzenesulphonyl chlorides in presence of dry pyridine to give 2-substituted 4-[6'(2'-sulphonamide/sulphanilamido-phenyl)-benzo thiazolyl]-thiazoles(IV).

The structure of the compounds were confirmed by sulphur analysis and IR spectra. The presence of free amino group in (I) was confirmed by diazotisation and also by IR spectra. The stretching absorption of free amino group was in the range of 3440-3280 cm^{-1} and bending absorption in the range of 1640-1630 cm^{-1} . The O=S=O in(II) showed the absorption frequency due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching at 1350 cm^{-1} and 1125 cm^{-1} respectively⁻¹.

Experimental

M.Ps. are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer - 137 Infracord.

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Preparation of 2-substituted-4(4'-aminophenyl)-thiazoles(I) :

A mixture of substituted thioamides (0.055 mol), *p*-acetamido-*w*-chloroacetophenone (0.05 mol) and ethyl alcohol (50 ml), was refluxed for one hour. The 2-substituted-4(4'-acetamidophenyl)-thiazoles were isolated following the method of Hantzsh⁹. These 4'-acetamidophenyl compounds were dissolved in alcohol (10 ml), 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (25 ml), and refluxed. The product was filtered and crystallised from ethyl alcohol.

The melting points, percentage yields and sulphur analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - 2-SUBSTITUTED-4(4'-AMINOPHENYL)-THIAZOLES

Substituent R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur% Found	Cal.
a. Methyl	142	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	16.51	16.84
b. Phenyl	204	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	12.55	12.70
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	202	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.49	10.77
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	162	49	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ SCl	10.01	11.18
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	119	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	11.81	12.03
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	151	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	11.11	11.34

TABLE 1A—2-SUBSTITUTED-1-(4-4'-PHENYL)-THIAZOLYL-THIOUREAS

Substituent R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur%	
				Found	Calcd.
a. Methyl	182	50	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	25.30	25.70
b. Phenyl	230	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	20.41	20.57
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	235	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂	17.62	17.97
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	202	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	18.89	18.55
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	204	49	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	19.72	19.70
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	271	53	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S ₂	18.91	18.76

Preparation of 2-substituted-4[6'(2'-amino)-benzothiazolyl]-thiazoles :

Compounds(I) were converted to their thiourea derivatives by Vijaykumaran method(IA). The thioureas (0.03 mol) were added to sulphuryl chloride (5 ml) in chlorobenzene. The reaction mixture was heated at 40° for one hour and then kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. The chlorobenzene was removed by steam distillation and the solution was neutralised by adding ammonia. The solid so obtained was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from aq. acetic acid. The physical constants are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—2-SUBSTITUTED-4-[6'(2'-AMINO)-BENZOTHAZOLYL]-THIAZOLES

Substituent R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur%	
				Found	Calcd.
a. Methyl	122	57	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂	25.71	25.90
b. Phenyl	164	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	20.48	20.70
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	174	75	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂	17.81	18.00
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	182	79	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	19.35	18.60
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	101-2	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	19.68	19.80
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	105-7	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S ₂	18.52	18.80

*General procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted-4-[4'-(*p*-substituted benzenesulphonamido)phenyl] and 2-substituted-4[6'(2'-sulphanilamido-N'-acetamido-sulphanilamido) benzothiazolyl]-thiazoles(II), (IV) :*

The (4'-aminophenyl) and (2'-amino-benzothiazolyl)-thiazoles (0.01 mol) were treated separately with freshly prepared *p*-substituted benzenesulphonyl chlorides (0.011 mol) in dry pyridine (20 ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for one hour and kept at room temperature for 36 hours. It was poured over ice-H₂SO₄ mixture. The product obtained was washed with dil. NaHCO₃ solution and finally with water. It was crystallised from aq. acetic acid. *p*-Methyl and *p*-acetamido-benzenesulphonyl chlorides were condensed with different 4-(4'-aminophenyl) and 4-[6'(2'-amino) benzothiazolyl]-thiazoles. The 4-(4'-N'-acetamidophenyl-sulphanilamido) and 4-[6'(2'-N'-acetamidophenyl-sulphanilamido)-benzothiazolyl]-thiazole derivatives were hydrolysed by 30% hydrochloric acid, to 4-(4'-sulphanilamidophenyl) and 4-[6'(2'-sulphanilamidophenyl)-benzothiazolyl]-thiazoles which were crystallised from a mixture of ethanol acetic acid.

The data are given in Tables 2 and 4.

Activity :

All the 4-(4'-sulphanilamidophenyl)-thiazoles and 4-[6'(2'-sulphanilamido)-benzothiazolyl]-2-substituted thiazoles were tested against *M. tuberculosis*, *V. comma*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*. It was found that some sulphanilamido compounds were active against *M. tuberculosis* while 2-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-(4'-sulphanilamidophenyl)-thiazoles, 2-methyl-4-[6'(2'-sulphanilamidophenyl)-benzothiazolyl]-thiazole and 2-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-6'(2'-sulphanilamidophenyl)-benzothiazolyl-thiazole were found to be effective up to

TABLE 2—2-SUBSTITUTED-4-(4'-(*p*-SUBSTITUTED BENZENESULPHONAMIDO)PHENYL)-THIAZOLES

Substituent R	Substituents R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur analysis%	
					Found	Calcd.
a. Methyl	-CH ₃	197	48	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	18.41	18.60
	-NHCOCH ₃	229	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	16.33	16.53
	-NH ₂	251	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	17.69	17.98
b. Phenyl	-CH ₃	137	40	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	16.40	16.24
	-NHCOCH ₃	208	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	14.31	14.65
	-NH ₂	160	49	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	16.20	16.20
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	-CH ₃	151	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	15.60	15.06
	-NHCOCH ₃	219	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	12.98	13.28
	-NH ₂	182	59	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	14.12	14.55
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	-CH ₃	141	45	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	14.72	14.95
	-NHCOCH ₃	120	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	13.88	14.07
	-NH ₂	110	46	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	14.88	14.92
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	-CH ₃	138	54	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	15.11	15.24
	-NHCOCH ₃	115	55	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.71	13.82
	-NH ₂	194	46	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	14.91	15.20
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	-CH ₃	124	67	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.85	14.16
	-NHCOCH ₃	186	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.05	13.36
	-NH ₂	168	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	14.28	14.65

TABLE 4—2-SUBSTITUTED-4[6'(2'-SULPHANILAMIDO N⁴-ACETAMIDOSULPHANILAMIDO)-BENZOTHAZOLYL]-THIAZOLES

Substituent R	Substituent R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Sulphur analysis %	
					Found	Calcd.
a. Methyl	-NHCOCH ₃	178	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	21.81	21.60
	-NH ₂	176	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	23.69	23.80
b. Phenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	145	53	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	18.55	18.90
	-NH ₂	132	57	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	20.51	20.60
c. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	151	71	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	17.10	17.40
	-NH ₂	107	49	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	18.59	18.80
d. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	120	44	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	17.61	17.70
	-NH ₂	111	51	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	18.08	18.30
e. <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	141	62	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	18.55	18.40
	-NH ₂	122	67	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	20.41	20.08
f. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	-NHCOCH ₃	304	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	17.85	17.90
	-NH ₂	285*	59	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄ S ₂	19.10	19.40

* Soften at

2 ug/ml. It is quite comparable to that of streptomycin (H 37 Rv/Strain).

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Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra of Some Drugs: Ephedrine, Metoclopramide and Chlorpheniramine

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CARBON-13 NMR spectra of biologically active organic compounds are of current interest¹. In our efforts to assign ¹³C NMR chemical shifts of

some potent drugs we now wish to report the assignment of ¹³C NMR spectra of ephedrine [α -hydroxy- β -methylaminopropylbenzene] (I), norephedrine [α -hydroxy- β -aminopropylbenzene] (II), metoclopramide [4-amino-5-chloro-2-methoxy-N-(β -diethylaminoethyl) benzamide] (III) and chlorpheniramine [γ -(4-chlorophenyl)- γ -(2-pyridyl)-propylidimethylamine] (IV). Ephedrine is used as sympathomimetic, vasoconstrictor and anti-allergic whereas metoclopramide and chlorpheniramine as antiemetic and antihistaminic respectively². The assignments of the carbon resonances of these drugs are of theoretical interest.

The ¹³C NMR spectra of all these compounds were taken in CDCl₃ as solvent as well as internal reference ($\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9$ ppm) whereas the spectra of their salts were obtained in D₂O with dioxane as internal reference ($\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{Dioxane} + 67.4$ ppm). The spectra were recorded on a Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20.1 MHz in the FT mode. In each case a proton noise decoupled and single frequency off-resonance decoupled (SFORD) spectra were run to establish carbon shifts and degree of protonation. Coupled spectra afforded the J_{C-H} values. A little variation in chemical shifts and coupling constants of the compounds with that of their salts is observed.

Ephedrine (I) and Norephedrine (II) :

The ¹³C NMR chemical shifts and coupling constants (J_{C-H}) of ephedrine and norephedrine and those of their hydrochlorides are enumerated in Table 1. C-1 experiences a downfield shift of about 11 ppm for the substituent present at C-1. The substituent has little effect on other aromatic carbons. A downfield shift of nearly 8 ppm is

